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Theory and practice of modern linguistic and methodological approaches to teaching English in digital education

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Abstract : Educational technologies mean the effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also involves improving the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. Currently, the role of a modern approach in language learning and teaching is incomparable.

Key words : computer technology, skills, interactive method, educational material, lesson, didactics, interactive method.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, great importance is attached to the study and teaching of foreign languages in our country. The Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching "Foreign Languages", adopted on December 10, 2012, expanded the opportunities for studying foreign languages. In our republic, new methods and requirements for teaching a foreign language and assessing the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of European countries (CEFR, IELTS, PIRLS, PISA). According to it, textbooks and educational materials are being created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. The demand for learning a foreign language is also increasing day by day. The subject of a foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, listening, comprehension and speaking), and a separate concept, qualification and skills are given for each of them. The use of technological tools is increasingly useful in every aspect of foreign language learning (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking) with interactive, non-traditional tasks. For example, for listening comprehension, this process is of course impossible without a computer, player, CDs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. It requires the learner to simultaneously pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meaning.

2 Methods

In the use of modern technologies in the educational process, it is also an important factor that students know and can use information and communication technologies well. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective methods, and it is also advisable to use it in a combination of a communicative approach and interactive tasks. In this process, including:

- When using computers, students have the opportunity to watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies, or cartoons, and at the same time learn by imitating them;
- the opportunity to listen to and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- to have a large language learning base through the use of smartphones and social networks, which are considered non-traditional methods;
- CD players can be used. The use of these technical means ensures that the process of learning a foreign language for students is more interesting and effective, in addition, through active games, students' attention is concentrated in one place during the lesson.

It is known that the use of various games in the lesson expands the capabilities of students, helps them to demonstrate their hidden abilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The teaching method, which is a combination of role-playing games and exercises aimed at finding solutions to problem situations, prevents students from being distracted during the lesson, and develops their skills in finding solutions to

problems and conducting independent research. Psychologists emphasize that the psychological mechanisms of action games are based on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. During the game process, the student approaches this activity with interest and acts freely, unlike in a regular lesson.

Today, we cannot imagine learning and teaching a language without computer technology. At the same time, the teacher no longer organizes a lesson in the traditional way by explaining all the information, but only by giving instructions and explanations, allowing students to independently search for information. This, in turn, requires an unusual system of innovative interactive tasks and lesson organization in the educational process. When interactive tasks are used, the spirit of competition, rivalry, and argumentation of students has a strong impact on their intellectual activity. This is manifested when people are looking for a solution to a problem in an organized way. In addition, such psychological factors influence and encourage them to express their own similar, close, or, conversely, completely opposite opinion to any opinion expressed by others. Below, we will separately consider the differences and effectiveness of interactive methods and tasks from the traditional educational process.

The potential of interactive methods and tasks in the educational process

Interactive method - serves to activate the assimilation of knowledge by students and the teacher in the educational process, to develop their personal qualities. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria of interactive education are: informal discussions, the ability to freely present and express educational material, a small number of lectures, but a large number of seminars, creating opportunities for students to take the initiative, giving assignments to work in small groups, large groups, class teams, performing written work and other methods, which are of particular importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work.

3 Results and discussion

Reasons for the effectiveness of interactive lessons

Currently, one of the main directions in the field of improving teaching methods is the introduction of interactive teaching and learning methods. Teachers of all subjects are increasingly using interactive methods in the process of lessons. As a result of the use of interactive methods, students' skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinion, defending it with justification, healthy communication, discussion, and debate are formed and developed. In this regard, the American psychologist and educator B. Bloom created a taxonomy of pedagogical goals in the cognitive and emotional spheres. B. Bloom's taxonomy is called. (Taxonomy is a theory of classification and systematization of complex structured areas of existence). He divided thinking into six levels in accordance with the development of cognitive abilities. According to him, the development of thinking occurs at the levels of knowing, understanding, applying, analyzing, generalizing, evaluating. Each of these levels is also represented by the following symbols and examples of verbs corresponding to each level, including: Knowing is the initial level of thinking, in which the student can name terms, knows specific rules, concepts, facts, and so on. Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking: to be able to repeat, to consolidate, to convey information, to tell, to write, to express, to distinguish, to recognize, to tell, to repeat. When having thinking at the level of understanding, the student understands facts, rules, schemes, tables. Based on the available information, he can roughly describe future consequences. Examples of verbs according to this level of thinking: to justify, to substitute, to clarify, to define, to explain, to translate, to rearrange, to illuminate, to interpret, to clarify.

In thinking at the level of application, the student can use the knowledge gained not only in traditional, but also in unconventional situations and apply them correctly. Examples of verbs at this level of thinking include: introduce, calculate, demonstrate, use, teach, determine, implement, calculate, apply, solve. At the analytical level of thinking, the student can distinguish parts of a whole and the relationships between them, see errors in the logic of thinking, distinguish between facts and consequences, and evaluate the significance of information. Examples of verbs at this level of thinking include: cause, separate, stratify, classify, guess, predict, distribute, distribute, verify, group.

At the level of generalization, students perform creative work, plan an experiment, use knowledge from several fields. Creatively process information to create something new. Examples of verbs corresponding to this level of thinking: create something new, generalize, combine, plan, develop, systematize, combine, create, construct, design. At the level of evaluation, students' language skills distinguish criteria, adhere to them, see the diversity of criteria, evaluate the correspondence of conclusions to available information, distinguish between facts and evaluative opinions. Examples of verbs corresponding to this level of thinking are: diagnose, prove, measure, control, justify, approve, evaluate, verify, compare, compare. Interactive methods are very diverse, and all of them, like any progressive methods, first of all require the teacher to make extensive preparation before the lesson. When

organizing these lessons, the main features of an interactive lesson can be more clearly perceived by considering some of its differences from a traditional lesson. For this purpose, we present the following table:

Differences between traditional and interactive lessons

№	Basic concepts	Traditional lesson	Interactive lesson
1	Application level	It is used in the form of lesson types that are convenient for them on all subjects.	For some topics, interactive lessons are used in the form of convenient types of lessons. For other topics, traditional lessons are used.
2	Lesson objective	Formation and consolidation of knowledge, skills, and competencies on the topic of the lesson.	To teach independent thinking, drawing conclusions, presenting them, and defending them on the topic of the lesson.
3	Teacher's duties and work methods	Explaining a new topic, reinforcing it, controlling it, giving assignments.	Organizing, managing, supervising students' independent work and presentations, and justifying final conclusions.
4	Requirements for lesson preparation	Preparation of lesson plans, syllabi and didactic tools.	Development of interactive lessons, tasks for independent work, handouts, and other necessary tools.
5	Requirements for student preparation	Complete the tasks for the lesson..	Knowledge of basic concepts and initial information on the topic of the new lesson.
6	Student tasks and methods	Listening to and mastering the teacher, completing the assigned tasks.	Independent thinking on completing assignments given by the teacher, comparing one's own thoughts and conclusions with others, and coming to a final conclusion
7	Time allocation	Most of the lesson time is spent on the teacher explaining and analyzing a new topic, explaining assignments, and monitoring mastery.	Most of the lesson time is spent on students completing independent assignments, exchanging ideas, observing, and presenting and defending their conclusions.
8	Modules and algorithms of the lesson	Each teacher uses the lesson modules and algorithms according to their own method.	Each lesson is conducted according to pre-prepared modules, algorithms, and projects.
9	Level of activity required from students	The teacher is active in all aspects, actively involved in students' concentration, understanding, thinking, and completing tasks. Communication forms: teacher-group; teacher-student student-student; student-teacher; group-teacher;	Both the teacher and the students are actively involved. Forms of cooperation and co-creation: Students - small group; teacher - small group - teacher; group - teacher.

10	The main methods of acquiring knowledge	Communication, discussion, negotiation, debate, reflection, analysis, observation, reading, etc.	Communication, reading, observation, discussion, negotiation, debate, reflection, analysis, etc.
11	Forms of training	Lecture, seminar, practical training, laboratory training, round table discussion, debate, discussion, consultancy, etc.	Lecture, group or pair work, presentations, debate, discussion, roundtable discussion, practical work, etc.
12	Expected result	Students' acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competencies on the topic.	To help students form their own opinions and conclusions on the topic, and to teach them to acquire knowledge independently.

This table summarizes the idea very briefly. The differences in the table clearly show the advantages and disadvantages of these two types of lessons compared to each other.

Based on the analysis of some aspects of interactive training shown in this table, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. When teaching subjects in the curriculum, it is necessary to consider which topics it is appropriate to organize interactive lessons on. This involves using interactive or traditional types of training that ensure the full achievement of the goal of the training on each topic.

2. For an interactive training to be effective, it is necessary to ensure that students know the basic concepts and initial information on the topic before a new training.

3. It is necessary to take into account that in an interactive training, more time is spent on independent work by students than in a traditional training.

About the impact of such differences in social life, A. Navoi wrote several centuries ago in the preface to his famous work "Mahbub ul-qulub": "I hope that readers will look at it with attention and attention, and each will benefit according to his own understanding and perception...". This shows that everyone can understand, assimilate, benefit from and apply this work in different ways, that is, only at the level of their own understanding and perception, and from this we can summarize our conclusions about the main differences between interactive teaching methods and traditional methods, and express it as the development of students' understanding and perception.

It should be noted that interactive teaching methods have been used in Uzbekistan since ancient times in the educational process in the form of discussions, debates, negotiations, observations, analysis, consultations, poetry readings, and readings in the communication between teachers and students and between students. These methods helped students develop their speech, thinking, reasoning, intellect, talent, and intelligence, helping them become independent-thinking, well-rounded individuals.

Currently, interactive methods are mainly used in conducting interactive training. In the future, these methods will be combined with interactive technology to some extent. In our opinion, the difference between the concepts of interactive methods and technology can be described as follows.

Interactive teaching method - implemented by each teacher at the level of available tools and their own capabilities. In this case, each student learns at a different rate, depending on their motivation and intellectual level. Interactive teaching technology - ensures that each teacher conducts a lesson that is understood by all students as if it were a lesson.

Within the framework of pedagogical technology, the following levels of mastering new educational material are identified: elementary, algorithmic, creative, and heuristic:

1). The initial level represents the student's ability to complete tasks based on what he has heard, examples given to him, and the presented algorithmic and instructional instructions. At this level of mastering the educational material, the teacher's activity and skill are more important. The teacher's ability to present the educational material in an interesting and coherent manner, to create problem situations, and to correctly determine the stages of the educational process constantly direct the student's activity.

2). Algorithmic level. It represents the ability of students to apply the knowledge and skills they have acquired in practice, as well as the ability to organize the activity of solving, recording and memorizing certain types of problems. At this level, the systematic nature of the educational material, the complexity of its content from easy to

difficult, ensuring intersubject and interdisciplinary connections, repetitions and demonstrativeness are of particular importance.

3). Creative level. This level represents the ability to apply educational material, as well as previously acquired knowledge and skills, in various situations. In this, encouraging research in the mastery of educational materials, creating problem situations, paying attention to the development of creative abilities, and expanding the possibilities of applying knowledge in practice play an important role.

4). Heuristic level. It is characterized by the ability to independently search for solutions to the presented educational problems and find new information to solve them. At this level, it is important to organize the student's independent activities, direct them to self-control, and stimulate talent.

Based on the above considerations, the pedagogical technology-based approach to the didactic design of educational materials is distinguished by the following aspects:

- educational materials are designed to consistently organize the educational process based on pedagogical technology and are used to implement the specified educational activities;
- the lesson determines the specific goal of mastering educational materials in accordance with the requirements of pedagogical technology;
- the process of pedagogical processing of the content of the textbook materials is carried out;
- the didactic function of the educational material is determined;
- the form, methods and means of presenting educational materials are determined;
- the level of mastering the content of educational materials and the guaranteed final result are developed.

4 Conclusion

Therefore, in order to improve the design of educational materials didactically and methodologically, and to implement them in the educational process, the teacher performs secondary processing of them, that is, the educational process is designed. When designing educational materials, special attention should be paid to increasing student activity. It is advisable to implement this task using interactive methods that are currently widely used in educational practice. The joint activities of the teacher and the student (under the influence of all didactic factors) are provided only within a fixed and conscious time frame. Educational texts occupy the main place as educational tools. Educational texts are currently being represented in new educational tools (electronic textbooks, videos, audio lessons, audio and video cassettes, video disks and other information technologies).

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